

RESULTS OF CLINICAL OBSERVATION OF PATIENTS AFTER SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF PERI-IMPLANT SOFT TISSUE RECESSION WITH HYALURONIC ACID INJECTION GEL CORRECTION

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Abstract. *Soft tissues surrounding dental implants play a key role in their stability and longevity. The healing and regeneration process of these tissues leads to the formation of soft tissue attachment, which not only serves a functional role but also acts as a protective barrier, preventing infections from penetrating from the oral cavity into the bone tissue. One of the key factors determining the health of soft tissues around implants is their regenerative ability. During implant placement, the body initiates a healing process in which the soft tissue structures adapt to the new object. Thus, studying the characteristics of soft tissue attachment around dental implants is a relevant and multifaceted task requiring attention from specialists in dentistry and prosthetics. Understanding these processes will help develop optimal treatment and prevention methods aimed at preserving the health and functionality of dental implants [6,15].*

Keywords: *dental implant, hyaluronic acid, connective tissue graft, oral mucosa, clinical study.*

During implant placement, the body initiates a healing process in which the soft tissue structures adapt to the new object. In the early stages of regeneration, cells responsible for connective tissue formation become activated, contributing to fibrous encapsulation around the implant. This encapsulation plays an important role in protecting the oral cavity from potential microbial infections that may arise due to tissue integrity disruption. Furthermore, it is crucial to consider various factors influencing the condition of soft tissues, such as implant quality, their placement in the jaw, the presence of periodontal diseases, and the patient's hygiene habits. For example, poor oral hygiene can lead to tissue inflammation, which may negatively affect implant integration [1,7,16,13].

A lack of attached keratinized gingiva significantly complicates access to the area around implants and prosthetic structures, which, in turn, increases the risk of inflammatory diseases such as peri-implantitis [3,9,11].

Biological width refers to the volume of gingival tissue located above the alveolar bone crest and includes both connective and epithelial components of the attached gingival complex. This anatomical element is critically important for the successful integration of teeth and implants into the surrounding gingival tissue, ensuring the necessary conditions for epithelial adhesion and connective tissue fiber attachment to the tooth or implant structure [2,5,8].

Moreover, biological width also affects the clinical outcomes of dental interventions, including tooth implantation. Sufficient gingival width contributes to the stability and longevity of implants, providing optimal conditions for osseointegration—a process in which the implant

firmly fuses with the alveolar bone. Understanding the significance of biological width and its structural components is fundamental to developing effective dental care protocols and preventing oral diseases. Therefore, when planning dental procedures, anatomical and individual patient characteristics should be considered to create optimal conditions for maintaining gingival and dental-implant complex health in the long term [4,12,14].

These conflicting results highlight the need for further multilayered research to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying inflammatory reactions in gingival tissues. It is important to consider that gingival inflammatory processes can be multifactorial and result from interactions between various biological and mechanical factors. Studies aimed at establishing a connection between gingival anatomical characteristics and clinical outcomes could significantly contribute to the diagnosis and prevention of peri-implant tissue diseases.

Objective of the Study. A comparative assessment of clinical changes in the oral cavity following the surgical treatment of soft tissue recession around dental implants in patients with and without hyaluronic acid correction.

Materials and Methods. The study involved 80 patients with previously placed dental implants who voluntarily participated after providing informed consent. All patients had completed prosthetic treatment for partial edentulism using fixed prosthetic structures supported by dental implants. The age range of the study participants was between 45 and 60 years. The patients had non-removable prosthetic constructions supported by dental implants in their oral cavities, with an average usage duration of **6.34±2.8 years**.

The prosthetic constructions were fixed exclusively using the screw-retained method. One of the inclusion criteria for the study was the presence of an access channel in the crowns and prostheses, allowing for the removal of the prosthetic construction at various study stages.

Patients were categorized into groups based on the degree of marginal gingival recession, classified according to **P. Miller (1985)**:

- **Group 1** – Patients with **Class II and III soft tissue recession** (according to P. Miller) who underwent surgical soft tissue volume restoration using a **free connective tissue graft**.
- **Group 2** – Patients with **Class II and III soft tissue recession** (according to P. Miller) who underwent surgical soft tissue volume restoration using a **free connective tissue graft with hyaluronic acid correction**.
- **Group 3** – Patients with **Class I soft tissue recession** around implants who received **only hyaluronic acid treatment**.
- **Group 4** – **Control group** (healthy individuals).

Table 1. Distribution of patients based on the degree of soft tissue recession according to P. Miller (1985).

	Class1	Class 2	Class3	Class4	Total
Group 1	30(100%)	-	-	-	20
Group 2	-	7(35%)	13(65%)	-	20
Group 3	-	10(50%)	10(50%)	-	20

Patients with **Class IV gingival recession** (according to P. Miller) were not included in the study, as this classification does not allow for complete recession coverage.

Surgical Treatment in Groups I and II

In **Groups I and II**, a **surgical method** was used to eliminate soft tissue recession around dental implants. In both groups, the **"envelope technique"** was applied for recession coverage

using a **connective tissue autograft**. However, in **Group II**, patients also received **injectable hyaluronic acid** during the surgical procedure and in the postoperative period.

Non-Surgical Approach in Group III

In **Group III**, the treatment involved a **non-surgical method** for soft tissue volume restoration using the "**Revident**" **injectable gel**. This is a **biodegradable, viscoelastic hyaluronic acid-based injectable gel**, derived through a staged interaction of **non-animal-origin hyaluronic acid** with the **AGEG 1/6 complex**, forming a supramolecular structure.

Method of Drug Administration. Following **topical anesthesia**, the **Revident gel** was injected into the **marginal gingiva adjacent to the implant-supported suprastructure** and/or into **interdental gingival papillae** at a **depth of 1 mm**. The volume of the injected suspension varied from **0.05 to 0.1 ml**.

Criteria for Effective Injection of Hyaluronic Acid Gel:

- Tension in the gingival tissue.
- Perifocal blanching of the mucosa at the injection site.
- Reverse leakage of the solution from the injection point.

Methods for Evaluating the Rehabilitation Period

The postoperative pain syndrome was assessed using the **standard 10-point Verbal Descriptor Scale** (Gaston-Johansson F., Albert M., Fagan E. et al., 1990).

Other clinical evaluation methods included:

- **Assessment of collateral edema and mucosal hyperemia:** Conducted visually on **days 1, 3, 5, and 7** postoperatively.
- **Epithelialization and fibrinous plaque formation:** Evaluated on **days 7, 14, and 21** through clinical examination.
- **Assessment of mucosal thickness changes:** Measured under **topical anesthesia** at **1, 3, 6, and 12 months** postoperatively.
- **Measurement of recession changes:** Conducted using a **periodontal probe** marked from **1 to 14 mm** (ASA DENTAL MC0703-14, Italy) at baseline and at **1, 3, 6, and 12 months** postoperatively.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1. Pain Syndrome Assessment in Patients from Groups I and II at Different Postoperative Time Points (n/%)

	Group 1						Group 2					
	0	1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10	0	1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10
1 st day	-	-	3 (15%)	9 (45%)	5 (25%)	3 (15%)	-	2 (10%)	4 (20%)	10 (50%)	3 (15%)	1 (5%)
3 rd day	-	3 (15%)	8 (40%)	7 (35%)	2 (10%)	-	-	5 (25%)	9 (45%)	5 (25%)	1 (5%)	-
7 th day	-	1 (5%)	14 (70%)	5 (25%)	-	-	-	8 (40%)	9 (45%)	3 (15%)	-	-
14 th day	10 (50%)	5 (25%)	5 (25%)	-	-	-	15 (75%)	4 (20%)	1 (5%)	-	-	-

On the first day after surgery, most patients reported severe pain: 45% in Group I and 50% in Group II. Unbearable pain was experienced by 14% of Group I and 5% of Group II. Very severe pain was noted in 25% of Group I and 15% of Group II. Moderate pain was reported by 15% of Group I and 20% of Group II, while mild pain was experienced by 10% of Group II. These

indicators reflect the body's active response to surgical intervention, but the lower pain intensity in Group II suggests a positive effect of hyaluronic acid in reducing inflammation.

Diagram: Pain Severity in Patients of Groups I and II at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%

On the third day, unbearable pain was absent in both groups. The proportion of complaints about very severe pain decreased threefold in Group II and 2.5 times in Group I. Severe pain was reported by 25% of Group II patients (half as many as on the first day) and 35% in Group I. Moderate pain was experienced by 25% of patients in both groups, while mild pain was noted in 25% of Group II and 15% of Group I. This indicates a significant reduction in inflammatory response and gradual tissue healing, with a more pronounced positive dynamic in Group II.

By the end of the first week, no complaints of very severe pain remained. Severe pain was reported by 25% of Group I and 15% of Group II. Moderate pain was observed in 45% of Group II and 75% of Group I. Mild pain was noted in 25% of Group II and 40% of Group I. No pain was experienced by patients in either group. These results demonstrate that the use of hyaluronic acid in the surgical site accelerates the recovery process and reduces pain intensity.

By the 14th day, 25% of Group II patients and 5% of Group I patients experienced moderate pain, while mild pain was noted in 25% of Group II and 20% of Group I. Complete pain relief was observed in 75% of Group I patients, which was 25% higher than in Group II. This can be explained by the fact that Group II patients experienced faster pain relief in the early stages, whereas the recovery process in Group I was more prolonged. These findings highlight the effectiveness of hyaluronic acid in minimizing pain and accelerating healing.

Table 2: Results of the Assessment of Collateral Soft Tissue Swelling in Patients of Groups I and II at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%.

	Group I				Group II			
	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3
1 st day	-	-	-	20(100%)	-	-	1(5%)	19(95%)
3 rd day	-	-	10(50%)	10(50%)	-	2(10%)	10(50%)	8(40%)
5 th day	4(20%)	8(40%)	8(40%)	-	7(35%)	9(45%)	4(20%)	-
7 th day	7(35%)	9(45%)	4(20%)	-	16(80%)	4(20%)	-	-

When analyzing the dynamics of postoperative swelling in both groups, pronounced symptoms were observed on the first day after surgery. In Group I, all patients (100%) exhibited

significant swelling, while in Group II, 19 patients (95%) experienced severe swelling. In contrast, 1 patient (5%) in Group II exhibited moderate swelling.

Diagram: Degree of Collateral Soft Tissue Swelling in Patients of Groups I and II at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%

By the third day, there were significant changes in the proportion of patients experiencing different levels of swelling intensity. The number and percentage of patients in Group II with pronounced swelling decreased by half compared to the previous assessment, with 10 patients (50%) still experiencing severe swelling. The remaining 10 patients (50%) in Group II displayed moderate swelling. Notably, Group II demonstrated a more positive trend in reducing collateral swelling intensity: half of the patients (10/50%) exhibited moderate swelling, similar to Group I. Meanwhile, 8 patients (40%) still showed significant swelling symptoms, and 2 patients (10%) exhibited only mild swelling.

By the fifth day after surgery, severe postoperative swelling was no longer observed in either group. In Group I, an equal number of patients exhibited moderate and mild swelling symptoms—8 patients (40%) in each category. In contrast, in Group II, the number of patients with moderate swelling was 4 (20%), which was 20% lower than in Group I. Additionally, 9 patients (45%) in Group II exhibited only mild swelling. Swelling was entirely absent in 4 patients (20%) in Group I and 7 patients (35%) in Group II, further indicating a more favorable postoperative tissue recovery trend in the group that received hyaluronic acid injections.

By the end of the first postoperative week, the swelling intensity had significantly improved in Group II. In 16 patients (80%), collateral swelling was completely absent, and only 4 patients (20%) exhibited mild swelling. In contrast, Group I showed less improvement compared to the previous assessment. Only 7 patients (35%) had no swelling, while nearly half of the group—9 patients (45%)—exhibited mild symptoms of collateral swelling, and 4 patients (20%) still showed significant swelling.

Table 3: Results of the Assessment of Wound Surface Epithelialization and Fibrinous Plaque in Patients of Groups I and II at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%.

	Group I			Group II		
	0	1	2	0	1	2
7 th day	-	1(5%)	9(45%)	7(35%)	8(40%)	5(25%)
14 th day	8(40%)	12(60%)	-	20(100%)	-	-
21 th day	20(100%)	-	-	20(100%)	-	-

One Week After Surgery

Almost all patients in Group I exhibited fibrinous plaque covering the wound surface along the incision line, with sutures remaining intact upon visual inspection. In 1 patient (5%), the fibrinous plaque appeared less pronounced. In Group II, 8 patients (40%) displayed fibrinous plaque of mild intensity, while 5 patients (25%) exhibited the highest intensity on the assessment scale. Notably, 7 patients (35%) in Group II showed no clinical signs of fibrinous plaque, indicating a more favorable healing process in the soft tissues surrounding the implant.

Two Weeks After Surgery

By the second postoperative week, all patients (100%) in Group II showed no fibrinous plaque, with complete epithelialization of the wound and removal of sutures. In contrast, in Group I, only 8 patients (40%) exhibited complete wound epithelialization and absence of fibrinous plaque. Meanwhile, in 12 patients (60%) of Group I, a thin fibrinous layer still covered the wound at the site of tissue fusion, and some sutures had shifted, though they remained intact.

Three Weeks After Surgery

By day 21 postoperatively, all 20 patients (100%) in Group I exhibited complete epithelialization of the postoperative wound, with no signs of fibrinous plaque.

Table 4: Results of the Assessment of Mucosal Thickness Changes in Patients of Groups I, II, and III at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%.

Group	Postoperative study periods			
	1 month	3 month	6 month	12 month
Group I	3,80±0,42	3,55±0,33	3,18±0,63	2,94±0,22
Group II	3,82±0,91	3,84±0,13	3,70±0,35	3,67±0,29
Group III	3,42±0,30	3,45±0,22	3,40±0,41	3,38±0,27

One Month After Surgery

The average mucosal thickness in Group I was **3.80 ± 0.42 mm**. In Group II, the thickness measured **3.82 ± 0.91 mm**, which was **0.53% higher** than in Group I. In Group III, the mucosal thickness was **3.42 ± 0.30 mm**, **10% lower** than in Group I.

Three Months After Surgery

In Group I, mucosal thickness decreased to **3.55 ± 0.33 mm**, reflecting a **6.58% reduction** compared to the first month. In contrast, Group II exhibited a slight increase to **3.84 ± 0.13 mm**, which was **8.17% higher** than in Group I. Group III showed a slight increase to **3.45 ± 0.22 mm**, remaining **2.82% lower** than in Group II.

Six Months After Surgery

In Group I, mucosal thickness continued to decrease to **3.18 ± 0.63 mm**, marking a **10.42% reduction** compared to the three-month mark. Group II showed only a minor decrease to **3.70 ± 0.35 mm**, remaining **16.35% higher** than in Group I. In Group III, mucosal thickness was **3.40 ± 0.41 mm**, showing a **minimal 1.45% decrease** compared to three months.

Twelve Months After Surgery

In Group I, mucosal thickness further declined to **2.94 ± 0.22 mm**, which was **22.63% lower** than at the one-month mark. Group II exhibited the highest stability in mucosal thickness, measuring **3.67 ± 0.29 mm**, only **3.93% lower** than at one month and **24.49% higher** than in Group I. Group III had a mucosal thickness of **3.38 ± 0.27 mm**, reflecting an **8.48% decrease** compared to the beginning of the study but still remaining higher than in Group I.

Conclusion. Throughout the study, **Group II demonstrated the highest stability and resistance in mucosal thickness**, thanks to the corrective effect of **hyaluronic acid gel injections**. The thickness in this group remained consistently higher than in other groups, confirming the effectiveness of the **combined approach**.

Group III, where **only hyaluronic acid gel injections** were applied, showed **stable mucosal thickness without significant fluctuations**, highlighting the independent effectiveness of this method in tissue regeneration.

Group I, which underwent **only surgical treatment**, experienced a **gradual reduction in mucosal thickness**, suggesting that this approach was **less effective** compared to Groups II and III.

Table 5: Results of the Assessment of Recession Changes in Patients of Groups I and II at Different Time Points After Surgery, n/%

Group	Postoperative study timeframes			
	1 month	3 month	6 month	12 month
I	2,82±1,02	2,45±1,03	2,28±1,13	2,03±0,9
II	3,32±1,42	2,70±1,02	3,03±0,7	2,90±1,12
III	0,93±0,52	1,02±0,31	1,15±0,55	1,00±0,23

Gingival Recession Reduction in Patient Groups

The degree of gingival recession decreased in both patient groups. In Group II, the recession was 17.7% lower than in Group I (3.32 mm vs. 2.82 mm).

Three months after surgery: The reduction in recession continued in both groups; however, the values in Group II remained lower (2.70 mm vs. 2.45 mm in Group I), with a difference of 10.2%.

Six months after surgery: The recession measured 2.28 mm in Group I and 3.03 mm in Group II. The reduction in recession was 32.9% more significant in Group II than in Group I.

Twelve months after surgery: The recession decreased to 2.03 mm in Group I and to 2.90 mm in Group II, showing a 42.9% difference between the groups, indicating the lasting effect of hyaluronic acid.

Data Analysis. The analysis showed that using hyaluronic acid in combination with surgical techniques contributed to a more pronounced reduction in gingival recession over the entire observation period. The improvement in Group II remained higher at every stage of the study, confirming the effectiveness of the combined approach.

Over the 12 months following surgery, both groups experienced a significant decrease in gingival recession:

- In Group I, the recession decreased by 28.01% compared to the baseline.
- In Group II, where hyaluronic acid was used, the reduction was 12.65%.

Despite the lower percentage reduction in Group II, the absolute values of recession remained lower than in Group I, confirming the effectiveness of hyaluronic acid in stabilizing the results.

Results in Group III. Group III, which underwent no surgical intervention and was treated solely with hyaluronic acid gel injections to correct soft tissue recession around the suprastructure, demonstrated the following results:

- **One month after observation:** The average gingival recession was 0.93 ± 0.52 mm, the lowest among all groups, reflecting the initially good condition of the soft tissues.

- **Three months after observation:** The recession slightly increased to 1.02 ± 0.31 mm, but the change remained minimal, indicating the stability of soft tissues.
- **Six months after observation:** A slight increase in recession to 1.15 ± 0.55 mm was observed, but this value remained significantly lower than in Groups I and II, confirming stable soft tissue conditions in this group.
- **Twelve months after observation:** The recession decreased to 1.00 ± 0.23 mm, demonstrating long-term stability without significant deterioration.

The results in Group III showed the most stable outcomes among all study groups. The average values of gingival recession remained within 0.93–1.15 mm throughout the observation period. The minimal changes confirm the effectiveness of the injection method for eliminating soft tissue recession around dental implants, eliminating the need for surgical intervention.

Conclusions. The use of hyaluronic acid in combination with surgical techniques contributed to a more significant and sustained increase in mucosal thickness compared to using a free connective tissue graft alone. This approach ensures not only a functional role but also a protective function of soft tissues, preventing peri-implantitis and other complications.

Patients who underwent hyaluronic acid correction experienced a faster reduction in pain. By the 14th day after surgery, 75% of patients in Group II were completely pain-free, which was 25% higher than in Group I.

Hyaluronic acid application accelerated the completion of wound epithelialization. After 14 days, all patients in Group II showed complete epithelialization without fibrinous plaque. Twelve months after treatment, Group II maintained a mucosal thickness 42.9% greater than Group I (2.90 mm vs. 2.03 mm), confirming the long-term effectiveness of the method.

Treatment methods involving hyaluronic acid demonstrated the absence of severe complications, good patient tolerance, and minimal side effects. The improvement in soft tissue condition and reduction of inflammatory processes contribute to an increased lifespan of dental implants, preventing the need for repeated surgical interventions.

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